

Dynamic Energy-Efficient User Plane Function Selection in 5G Networks

Shima Afshar Borji

DITEN - University of Genoa
Genoa, Italy
shima.afshar.borji@edu.unige.it

Roberto Bruschi

DITEN - University of Genoa
CNIT – S2N National Lab
Genoa, Italy
roberto.bruschi@unige.it

Cristina Emilia Costa

CNIT – S2N National Lab
Genoa, Italy
ccosta@cnit.it

Chiara Lombardo

DITEN - University of Genoa
CNIT – S2N National Lab
Genoa, Italy
chiara.lombardo@unige.it

Abstract—As 5G networks expand, managing the energy consumption of core components like the User Plane Function (UPF) becomes critical. Traditional static UPF deployments struggle with dynamic traffic patterns, leading to significant energy waste during off-peak hours or potential performance bottlenecks during peak times. This paper proposes a framework for dynamic UPF selection that leverages traffic prediction and UPF profiling to optimize energy efficiency while maintaining service performance. We profile two distinct UPF implementations—a user-space OpenAirInterface (OAI) solution and an SD-Core Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK)-based solution—characterizing their power consumption and performance across various throughput levels. A lightweight Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model is employed to predict near-term traffic load based on historical patterns. A utility function, weighting both predicted performance score and power efficiency, guides the selection between the User-Space and DPDK UPFs. Switching logic incorporating hysteresis and hold-down timers minimizes excessive transitions. Simulation results over a 7-day period using scaled historical traffic data demonstrate that the proposed dynamic strategy can achieve energy savings of approximately 9.59% compared to the best static UPF deployment, with a minimal performance impact of 2.19%. The framework provides a practical approach to enhancing the energy efficiency and sustainability of 5G network operations.

Index Terms—5G, User Plane Function (UPF), Energy Efficiency, Network Function Virtualization (NFV), Traffic Forecasting, LSTM, Dynamic Resource Allocation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The implementation of 5G and beyond networks promises significant connectivity with higher data rates, lower latency, and increased capacity. However, this advancement comes at the cost of significantly increased energy consumption within the network infrastructure [1]. The growing number of base stations, the deployment of edge computing resources, and the complexity of the 5G Core (5GC) contribute substantially to this energy footprint, causing challenges for operational costs and environmental sustainability [2]. Enhancing energy efficiency is essential for the sustainable operation of future mobile networks.

Within the 5GC, the UPF is a critical component responsible for packet routing, forwarding, Quality of Service (QoS) handling, and usage reporting. Its central role in data plane processing makes it a significant contributor to overall core network energy consumption [3]. The challenge is amplified

by the highly dynamic nature of mobile network traffic, which varies significantly based on the time of day, user mobility, and specific events. Many current deployments utilize static UPF configurations, often dimensioned for peak loads. This leads to substantial energy waste during periods of low traffic when resources are underutilized.

Furthermore, the 5G ecosystem allows for diverse UPF implementations, ranging from software-based user-space applications to high-performance kernel-bypass solutions utilizing frameworks like the Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) and potentially programmable P4-based options [4]. Each implementation presents a unique trade-off between performance and energy consumption. Static allocation fails to leverage these differences dynamically based on real-time network conditions. While some research has explored dynamic UPF placement and chaining [5], [6], a practical framework integrating prediction with selection between distinct implementation types based on energy-performance profiles needs further investigation.

To address these challenges, this paper proposes and evaluates a framework for dynamic, energy-efficient UPF selection. Our approach combines:

- 1) **UPF Profiling:** Experimental assessment of power consumption and performance metrics for different UPF implementations (OAI user-space and SD-Core's DPDK-based) under varying traffic loads.
- 2) **Traffic Forecasting:** Utilizing a lightweight LSTM model trained on historical data to predict near-term traffic demand.
- 3) **Utility-Based Decision Engine:** Employing a utility function that weights performance (derived from multiple QoS metrics) and power efficiency (derived from power consumption models) to determine the optimal UPF for the predicted traffic.
- 4) **Controlled Switching Logic:** Integrating hysteresis margins and hold-down timers to prevent excessive switching while considering the non-negligible costs associated with restarting UPF instances.

We simulate this framework using scaled historical traffic data and evaluate its effectiveness in terms of energy savings, performance impact, and switching frequency compared to

static baseline scenarios. The results demonstrate the potential for significant energy reduction through intelligent and adaptive UPF management.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II provides the related work. Section III details the proposed framework, including profiling, modeling, prediction, and the decision algorithm. Section IV presents the simulation results and analysis. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and discusses future work.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. The 5G UPF

The UPF is a fundamental component of the 5G Core network's data plane. Defined by 3GPP standards, it acts as an anchor point for mobility between radio access technologies (RATs) and provides the connection to Data Networks (DNs). Its key responsibilities include packet routing and forwarding, packet inspection, policy rule enforcement, traffic usage reporting, QoS handling, and lawful interception capabilities [4]. Due to its intensive role, the UPF's performance and energy consumption are critical factors in overall network efficiency. The NFV allows UPFs to be deployed as software instances, offering flexibility but also introducing performance variations based on the underlying software architecture and hardware acceleration techniques used.

B. UPF Implementations

Several approaches exist for implementing UPFs:

- **User-Space Applications:** Often developed for flexibility and ease of deployment, potentially running within standard operating system environments. Solutions like the OAI core network provide examples [7]. These may have lower performance but potentially lower baseline energy consumption compared to highly optimized solutions.
- **DPDK:** These implementations bypass the kernel's networking stack to achieve high packet processing throughput and low latency. Projects like SD-Core provide DPDK-based UPF modes [8]. They typically offer superior performance at high loads but may consume more power, especially at idle or low loads, due to polling mode drivers that continuously utilize dedicated CPU cores at 100% workload.
- **Programmable Data Planes (P4):** P4 allows for programming the forwarding behavior of network devices, enabling high performance and flexibility. However, P4-based UPFs are not yet common in practical deployments due to their reliance on specialized hardware [4].

This study compares the empirically measured performance characteristics of OAI's user-space UPF and SD-Core's DPDK-based UPF.

C. Energy Efficiency in 5G

The increasing energy demand of 5G has spurred research into various energy-saving techniques. These include sleep modes for base stations, cell zooming, optimization of radio resource management, and energy-aware cloud/edge resource

allocation [9]. Within the core network, virtualized function placement and dynamic resource scaling are key areas. Our work contributes to this field by specifically targeting the energy consumption of the UPF, a major data plane element.

D. Dynamic UPF Selection and Resource Allocation

Previous studies have recognized the potential benefits of dynamically managing UPF resources. Work by Alevizaki et al. [5] explored dynamic UPF allocation enabled by optical network nodes. [6] addressed the placement and chaining problem for user plane functions. While these studies highlight the need for dynamism, they often focus on placement or theoretical resource allocation rather than the practical selection between different available UPF software implementations with distinct energy-performance profiles based on predicted traffic, which is the focus of our work. Integrating realistic switching costs and control mechanisms like hysteresis is also a key practical aspect addressed here.

E. Network Traffic Forecasting

Accurate traffic forecasting is crucial for enabling proactive network resource management. While various time series forecasting techniques exist, ranging from traditional statistical models (e.g. Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)) to more advanced machine learning approaches, the primary goal in this context is to obtain a sufficiently reliable prediction of near-term traffic load. This prediction serves as a key input for the decision-making process regarding UPF selection. Methods like LSTM networks, a type of recurrent neural network, have demonstrated effectiveness in capturing temporal dependencies inherent in network traffic data, making them suitable for this task. Although exploring and comparing the nuances of different forecasting models is a research area in itself, the focus of this paper is on utilizing a capable forecasting model (specifically, an LSTM) to drive the dynamic selection mechanism, rather than on optimizing the prediction methodology itself. The quality of the forecast directly impacts the effectiveness of the dynamic UPF selection strategy in achieving energy efficiency while maintaining performance.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section details the framework developed to dynamically select UPF implementations (OAI User-Space vs. SD-Core DPDK-based) in a 5G network environment, aiming to minimize energy consumption while maintaining acceptable performance levels. The methodology integrates traffic prediction, UPF performance/power profiling, a utility-based decision engine, and simulation-based evaluation and optimization.

A. System Setup

To establish the performance and energy characteristics of different UPF implementations, empirical data was collected within a fully operational 5G test environment deployed on bare-metal servers. This infrastructure featured:

- **SD-Core UPF:** A high-throughput, DPDK-based UPF from the SD-Core project, leveraging hardware acceleration on an AMD EPYC 9474F processor with 512GB RAM and a 100Gbps Network Interface Card (NIC). This corresponds to the "DPDK-UPF" referred to in this study.
- **User-Space UPF:** A software-based UPF deployed by OpenAirInterface Core, handling packets in user-space on an Intel Xeon E5-2680 v4 processor with 256GB RAM and a 40Gbps NIC. This corresponds to the "OAI-UPF" referred to in this study.

Traffic loads were generated using Keysight LoadCore [10], leveraging two dedicated agents to simulate network behavior. The first agent, acting as the Next-Generation Radio Access Network (NGRAN) simulator (as shown in Fig. 1), emulated User Equipment (UE) and Radio Access Network (RAN) behavior, while the second agent functioned as the Data Network (DN) simulator. This setup enabled stress-testing of UPF performance across diverse scenarios, with traffic loads systematically varied. Power consumption was monitored via Scaphandre, while network performance metrics (including throughput, uplink/downlink delay, uplink/downlink jitter, and packet loss) were collected from the LoadCore platform to correlate energy usage with operational efficiency.

Fig. 1: Simplified Testbed Setup Diagram.

B. Performance Score Formulation

To quantify the overall QoS, a composite Performance Score, $P_u(T)$; ranging from 0 to 100, with higher values indicating superior quality, was formulated. This score combines multiple performance metrics, each normalised and weighted according to its importance.

Each metric M was normalised to a 0–100 scale based on its observed minimum (Min_M) and maximum (Max_M) values across the profiling data for both UPFs.

- For "higher-is-better" metrics (e.g., throughput):

$$\text{Norm}_M = 100 \times \frac{M - \text{Min}_M}{\text{Max}_M - \text{Min}_M} \quad (1)$$

- For "lower-is-better" metrics (e.g., Delay, Loss, Jitter, CPU):

$$\text{Norm}_M = 100 \times \frac{\text{Max}_M - M}{\text{Max}_M - \text{Min}_M} \quad (2)$$

Each normalised metric was assigned a weight (w_M) reflecting its contribution to overall performance ($\sum w_M = 1.0$). For each UPF type $u \in \{\text{OAI-UPF}, \text{DPDK-UPF}\}$, we define the final score as:

$$P_u(T) = \sum_{M_u} (w_{M_u} \times \text{Norm}_{M_u}(T)) \quad (3)$$

where the sum is over all selected metrics evaluated at throughput T using the polynomial models. Initially, certain particular weights were used; later, they were optimised. (Section III-H).

C. Energy Efficiency Score

Power consumption (W) was normalised across the global minimum ($W_{\text{min,global}}$) and maximum ($W_{\text{max,global}}$) power values observed for both UPFs within the relevant operational throughput range. Lower power yields a higher score:

$$E_u(T) = 100 \times \frac{W_{\text{max,global}} - W(T)}{W_{\text{max,global}} - W_{\text{min,global}}} \quad (4)$$

This score was clipped to $[0, 100]$.

D. Utility Function Definition

To directly model the trade-off between performance and energy efficiency, a Utility function was defined. This combines the Performance Score with a normalized Energy Efficiency Score.

The overall utility is a weighted sum:

$$U_u(T) = \alpha \cdot P_u(T) + \beta \cdot E_u(T) \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$: Weights for performance vs. energy ($\alpha + \beta = 1$) and represent prioritisation between performance or power efficiency.

E. Traffic Data and Preprocessing

The historical network traffic data used in this study is sourced from the NetMob 2023 dataset [11], which offers high-resolution, service-level mobile traffic information collected across 20 metropolitan areas in France over a 77-day period in 2019. This dataset provides traffic demand measurements at 15-minute intervals, capturing real-world patterns of various mobile applications. For this analysis, the focus is on video streaming services, such as Netflix.

Given that the dataset contains normalised traffic values—lacking explicit units to preserve confidentiality—the time series data were scaled to align with the minimum capacity of the UPF. This scaling assumes that only traffic manageable by the UPF with the lowest capacity will be steered, ensuring consistency between the dataset's magnitude and the system's operational thresholds.

F. Traffic Forecasting Model

To predict near-term traffic demand, an LSTM model was developed and employed. The model architecture consists of

- An LSTM layer with 50 units, designed to process sequences of historical traffic data. Based on the training data shape, input sequences representing the past 24 hours (96 intervals of 15 minutes) were used.
- A dropout layer following the LSTM layer to mitigate overfitting.
- A final dense (fully connected) layer with a single output unit, providing the traffic prediction for the next 15-minute interval.

It was trained on scaled historical traffic data derived from the NetMob 2023 dataset (as described in Section III-E), using past traffic patterns to predict the load for the subsequent interval. Performance during training was monitored using metrics such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE). This predictive model provides the crucial input for our dynamic UPF selection algorithm.

G. Dynamic UPF Selection Algorithm & Simulation

The simulation proceeds interval by interval, corresponding to the 15-minute granularity of the traffic data. In essence, for each interval i :

- 1) **Traffic Prediction:** The LSTM model forecasts the expected traffic load ($T_{\text{predicted}}$) for the upcoming interval based on the historical data observed up to interval $i - 1$. This employs a rolling forecast methodology, where the input sequence for the model is updated with the actual observed value for the interval i before predicting the interval $i + 1$.
- 2) **Candidate UPF Selection:** The decision engine evaluates the utility function $\mathcal{U}(T_{\text{predicted}})$ for both OAI-UPF and DPDK-UPF using the predicted traffic and the optimal weights α, β found during the optimization phase (Section III-H). The UPF implementation resulting in the higher utility score is determined as the theoretically ideal UPF ($\text{UPF}_{\text{ideal}}$) for the predicted conditions.
- 3) **Switching Control Mechanism:** To prevent excessive switching due to prediction noise or traffic fluctuations near the decision threshold and to account for the overhead of UPF transitions, two control mechanisms are applied before initiating a switch from the currently active UPF ($\text{UPF}_{\text{current}}$) to $\text{UPF}_{\text{ideal}}$:

- **Hold-down Timer:** A switch is only considered if the $\text{UPF}_{\text{current}}$ has been active for a minimum duration of I_{hold} intervals. This prevents rapid oscillations.
- **Hysteresis Margin:** A switch is only triggered if the predicted traffic \hat{T}_i not only crosses the utility crossover threshold ($T_{\text{crossover}}$), but also exceeds it by a defined margin (m_{hyst}). This margin helps filter out small fluctuations due to prediction noise. The hysteresis margin is defined as:

$$m_{\text{hyst}} = k \cdot \text{MAE}_{\text{in}} \quad (6)$$

where k is a tunable sensitivity constant and MAE_{in} is the in-sample Mean Absolute Error of the traffic predictor.

The switching decision rule then becomes:

$$\text{UPF}_{\text{ideal}} = \begin{cases} \text{DPDK-UPF}, & \text{if } \hat{T}_i > T_{\text{crossover}} + m_{\text{hyst}} \\ \text{OAI-UPF}, & \text{if } \hat{T}_i < T_{\text{crossover}} - m_{\text{hyst}} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

- 4) **State Update and Cost Accounting:** If both control conditions permit a switch, the $\text{UPF}_{\text{current}}$ state is updated to $\text{UPF}_{\text{ideal}}$. The associated downtime cost (the delay caused by switching) is added to the total downtime.

H. Utility Weight Optimization

To determine the optimal trade-off between performance and energy efficiency, the simulation (Section III-G) was run iteratively across a range of β values. For each value of β , the corresponding utility crossover threshold $T_{\text{crossover}}$ was recalculated and applied in the simulation.

The objective was to maximize energy savings while ensuring acceptable service quality. The optimal utility weights were selected under the constraint that the average performance score must remain at or above 70.0, or that the performance degradation does not exceed 5.0%.

I. Evaluation Metrics

The dynamic strategy is compared against static always-OAI and always-DPDK baselines using total energy consumed (Wh), average performance score, energy saving (%), performance change (%), switch count, total downtime (s), and percentage downtime (%). Comparisons are relative to the most energy-efficient static baseline.

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the results obtained by applying the methodology described in Section III.

A. UPF Profiling and Model Fitting

The profiling confirmed distinct energy-performance characteristics for the User-space UPF and DPDK-based UPF implementations. Polynomial regression generated functions that accurately modelled the observed data. Key observations include:

- **Performance:** DPDK-UPF generally offered lower average delay, particularly at higher throughputs. OAI-UPF's delay increased more significantly as load increased. OAI-UPF can only handle throughput up to 600 Mbps. In terms of CPU utilization, as expected, DPDK-UPF is always at 100% workload, while OAI-UPF CPU load increases as the traffic load increases.
- **Performance Score:** The overall performance score reflected these trade-offs, with OAI-UPF typically scoring slightly higher at low throughputs (below approx. 27 Mbps) and DPDK-UPF scoring higher at high throughputs (Figure 2).
- **Power Consumption:** OAI-UPF exhibited significantly lower idle power and lower power consumption at low

throughput levels (below approx. 90 Mbps). DPDK-UPF showed higher idle power but scaled more efficiently at higher throughputs, consuming less power (Figure 2).

Fig. 2: Visualization of actual measurements and polynomial approximations for power consumption and performance score of the UPFs.

B. Traffic Forecasting

The LSTM model was trained on 2688 intervals of scaled historical data. Figure 3 illustrates the model’s one-step-ahead predictions against the actual scaled traffic during the test period. The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for these predictions was 23.38 Mbps. The in-sample MAE on the training set, used for setting the hysteresis margin, was 24.31 Mbps.

C. Optimal Utility Weights and Crossover

The optimization process iterated through $Weight_Power$ values from 0 to 1. Maximizing energy savings while satisfying the performance constraint (Avg. Perf. Score ≥ 70 / Perf. Change $\geq -5\%$), yielded the optimal weights:

- Optimal $Weight_Performance$ (α): 0.2
- Optimal $Weight_Power$ (β): 0.8

For these weights, the utility crossover point ($T_{crossover}$) was calculated at approximately **95.6** Mbps.

D. Simulation Results with Optimal Weights

The dynamic UPF selection algorithm was simulated over the 672 interval (168 hours) test period using the optimal utility weights ($\alpha = 0.2$, $\beta = 0.8$), the LSTM predictor,

a hysteresis margin of 50 Mbps, and a hold-down timer of 4 intervals. Table I summarizes the key findings compared to static baselines. Figure 3 visualizes the traffic, predictions, and dynamic UPF selection over the simulation period.

The results demonstrate that the dynamic strategy achieved an energy saving of **9.59%** compared to the most efficient static baseline (DPDK-UPF). This saving was accompanied by a performance change of **2.19%**. The system performed 15 switches over the 168-hour (7 days) simulation period (approximately twice a day), resulting in 0.078% estimated downtime. The visualization in Figure 3 confirms that switches generally occur when predicted traffic crosses the operational zones defined by the utility crossover and hysteresis margin, while the hold-down timer prevents excessive flapping.

E. Sensitivity Analysis

The optimisation results show the sensitivity to utility weights. Prioritising performance (higher α) reduced energy savings but maintained higher average performance scores. Conversely, prioritising power efficiency, although the performance change for these UPFs is not significant and remains less than 1% even while solely prioritising power efficiency ($\beta = 1$), even showing a positive change compared to the best baseline, the results are shown for said weights. Sensitivity to switching control parameters was also observed; for instance, increasing the hold-down timer reduced the switch count and downtime but potentially delayed transitions to a more energy-efficient UPF, slightly decreasing overall savings. The chosen optimal parameters represent a specific balance based on the defined performance constraints.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper proposed a dynamic, energy-efficient UPF selection framework for 5G networks using traffic prediction and UPF profiling. We compared user-space OAI-UPF and DPDK-UPF, modeled their energy-performance trade-offs with polynomial functions, and used a lightweight LSTM to forecast traffic. A utility function balancing performance and energy guided the switching, supported by practical controls such as hysteresis and downtime estimation.

Simulation results show that dynamic switching can save approximately **9.59%** energy with a slight performance improvement of **2.19%** compared to static deployments. With 15 switches and about 8 minutes of downtime over a 7-day simulation, the approach demonstrates potential for adaptive and sustainable 5G network management.

Limitations of this study include the use of a basic one-step-ahead LSTM for traffic prediction, chosen to keep the focus on the selection mechanism. Evaluation was limited to simulations due to data constraints, and the switching cost model mainly considered downtime, omitting energy overhead during startup.

Overall, this work presents a practical methodology and highlights the potential of intelligent UPF selection to enhance energy efficiency in 5G core networks.

TABLE I: Simulation Results Summary with Optimal Utility Weights ($\alpha=0, \beta=1$)

Metric	Dynamic Strategy	Always-OAI Baseline	Always-DPDK Baseline	Comparison vs Best (DPDK-UPF)
Total Energy (Wh)	124.48	225.63	137.69	9.52% Saving
Avg. Performance Score	86.02	82.04	84.17	2.19% Change
Total Switches	15	0	0	-
Total Downtime (s)	473.0	0	0	-
Downtime Percentage (%)	0.078%	0%	0%	-

Fig. 3: Simulation Visualization: Actual Traffic, Predicted Traffic, and Active UPF State over the Test Period.

(a) Power Consumption

(b) Performance Score

Fig. 4: Visualization of Dynamic Solution’s Performance Score and Power Consumption compared to static baseline.

REFERENCES

[1] Y. Ding, H. Duan, M. Xie, R. Mao, J. J. Wang, and W. Zhang, “Carbon emissions and mitigation potentials of 5g base station in china,” *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, vol. 182, p. 106330, 2022.

[2] A. Mughees, M. Tahir, M. A. Sheikh, and A. Ahad, “Towards energy efficient 5g networks using machine learning: Taxonomy, research challenges, and future research directions,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 187 498–187 522, 2020.

[3] A. Bellin, N. D. Cicco, D. Munaretto, and F. Granelli, “Power consumption-aware 5g edge upf selection using deep reinforcement learning,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (NFV-SDN)*, 2024, pp. 1–6.

[4] J. Rischke, C. Vielhaus, P. Sossalla, J. Wang, and F. H. P. Fitzek, “Comparison of upf acceleration technologies and their tail-latency for urllc,” in *2022 IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (NFV-SDN)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 146–151.

[5] V. M. Alevizaki, A. I. Manolopoulos, M. Anastasopoulos, and A. Tzanakaki, “Dynamic user plane function allocation in 5g networks enabled by optical network nodes,” in *2021 European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–4.

[6] I. Leyva-Pupo and C. Cervelló-Pastor, “Efficient solutions to the placement and chaining problem of user plane functions in 5g networks,” *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 197, p. 103253, 2022.

[7] OpenAirInterface, “Openairinterface: 5g software alliance for democratizing wireless innovation,” <https://openairinterface.org>.

[8] O. N. F. (ONF), “Sd-core,” <https://opennetworking.org/sd-core/>.

[9] D. A. Milovanovic and Z. Bojković, “Exploring 5g/6g energy-efficiency in mobile communications for sustainable future,” 2025, pp. 259–292. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003511298-13>

[10] Keysight, “P8900s loadcore – core network solutions,” <https://www.keysight.com/us/en/product/P8900S/loadcore-core-network-solutions.html>.

[11] O. E. Martínez-Durive, S. Mishra, C. Ziemlicki, S. Rubrichi, Z. Smoreda, and M. Fiore, “The netmob23 dataset: A high-resolution multi-region service-level mobile data traffic cartography,” 2023.